

This is apparently accomplished by elimination of the elements of acetic acid molecule⁴. I.R. absorption spectrum of this compound showed characteristic bands at 1680 cm^{-1} (N-acetyl), $1190, 1160\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the cyclic -C-O-C- group and at 1580 cm^{-1} for C=N. This compound exhibits a magenta colour in concentrated sulphuric acid.

Interaction of the aminophenothiazine with benzyl chloride: This reaction gave different products according to the amount of benzyl chloride used. Thus with equimolecular amounts of (I) and benzyl chloride, the resulting product was identified as 2-phenyloxazolo [4,5-*b*] phenothiazine(III, Ar=phenyl), whereby, with two moles of benzyl chloride the product was 2-phenyl-5-benzylloxazolo [4, 5-*b*] phenothiazine (IX, Ar=phenyl).

Transformation of the former to the latter was easily effected by heating with benzyl chloride thus confirming the route of the reaction, (Scheme b).

Scheme b

Other N-benzylloxazolophenothiazines were prepared by the action of benzyl chloride on different 2-aryloxazolophenothiazines. It must be mentioned that this reaction proceeds smoothly if the aryl group of (III) contains electron withdrawing group.

Unlike to (III) the N-benzyl derivatives (IX) are unaffected by concentrated hydrochloric acid, this demonstrates clearly the effect of substituents on the stability of the oxazole ring. I.R.⁵ absorption spectra of (IX) indicated the absence of the band at 3340 cm^{-1} , characteristic for a secondary amino group. These compounds are yellow to cream in colour with melting

points lower than the corresponding oxazolophenothiazines and exhibited an intense violet to green fluorescence in concentrated sulphuric acid.

The above described oxazolophenothiazines are considered to be suitable compounds for the preparation of heterocyclic dyes. Accordingly 2-(*p*-nitrophenyl) oxazolo [4,5-*b*] phenothiazine was reduced⁶ to the corresponding amino compound, which could only be diazotized by nitrosylsulphuric acid and the resulting diazonium salt was coupled with various components to give some interesting azoic dyes, which could be used for dyeing cotton and wool or synthetic fibres according

to the type of the coupler. These dyes showed good substantivity and fastness properties⁷.

Some of the hitherto synthesized oxazolophenothiazines (III), and (IX) were tested *in vitro* for their biological activities on some bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Sarcina lutea* and *Bacillus subtilis*.

Remarkable effects were obtained at concentrations of 1×10^{-1} to $1 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M}$. The N-substituted oxazolophenothiazines (IX) showed superior biological activity than the corresponding oxazolophenothiazines in all experiments.

On the other hand the role of substituent in (III) or (IX) is of no considerable value in this connection and the main effect is attributed to the thiazine nucleus. Concentration at $10^{-5} M$ gave 100% inhibition in case of 2-(*p*-nitrophenyl) oxazolophenothiazine and the corresponding 5-benzyl derivative in all tests.

Experimental

Melting points taken on a Mel-Temp. electrically heated, melting point unit and are uncorrected. The infrared absorption spectra were determined with a Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer using KBr wafer technique. The uv spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet recording spectrophotometer using 1 cm. matched cells and spectrally pure solvents.

3-aminophenothiaz-2-one (I): This was prepared according to the method of Abbadly and Osman¹.

2-Aryl-5H-Oxazolo [4,5-b] phenothiazines (III):

(i) Fusion method:

The aminophenothiazone (1 mol) was covered with the aromatic aldehyde (2 mol) and refluxed in an oil bath for thirty minutes but in the case of nitroaldehyde the mixture was heated in the direct flame for three minutes only. The reaction mixture was cooled, triturated with few ml of alcohol, the solid product was collected and washed several times with ethyl alcohol, then recrystallized from the proper solvent.

(ii) Solvent method:

Aminophenothiazone (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) were refluxed for 4 hours in *n*-butanol (20 ml) in the presence of dry piperidine (0.002 mol). The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting product was collected, washed with dilute alcohol, then crystallized from the proper solvent. In the case of liquid aromatic aldehydes, few drops of alcoholic ferric chloride solution must be added at the end of the reflux to promote the formation of the expected oxazoles. The results are listed in Table 1.

5H-Oxazolo [4,5-b] phenothiazine (VI): A mixture of (I), (0.01 mol), zinc dust (3 g.) and conc. HCl (10 ml) was refluxed for 20 min., the mixture was filtered rapidly, formamide (0.03 mol) was added to the filtrate. This mixture was refluxed for 20 min. in the presence of hydrogen chloride gas, the mixture was cooled, then extracted with benzene or light petroleum (80-100°). The extracted substance was collected and recrystallized from ethanol into pale green needles, m.p. 210°. Anal. Calcd. for: $C_{18}H_{18}N_2OS$: C, 65.00; H, 3.33; N, 11.66; S, 13.13. Found: C, 65.15; H, 3.25; N, 11.52; S, 13.09.

2-Methyl-5-acetyl-oxazolo[4,5-b]phenothiazine(VII):

(i) Preparation of 3-acetylamino-2-acetoxy-5-N-acetylphenothiazine (VIII):

To a colourless mixture of I (1 g.) in 10 ml. glacial acetic acid and zinc dust, 3 ml acetic anhydride was added. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 10 min., filtered, diluted with water to 100 ml. and left in a refrigerator overnight. The precipitated solid was crystallized twice from propyl alcohol. Yield (0.26 g) colourless crystalline material, m.p. 227-228°, soluble in ethanol, sparingly in benzene and ether.

The i.r. absorption spectrum of this molecule shows characteristic bands at 1770 cm^{-1} (aromatic acetate), 1675 cm^{-1} (N-acetyl) and 1720 cm^{-1} (acetylamino). Anal. Calcd. For $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_4S$: C, 60.66; H, 4.42; N, 7.86; S, 9.00. Found: C, 61.13; 61.18; H, 3.90; 4.05; N, 8.06; 8.23; S, 8.79, 2.81%.

(ii) Fusion of triacetate (VIII) and preparation of (VII): A pure sample of 3-acetylamino-2-acetoxy-5-N-acetyl-phenothiazine (VIII) (4 g) was heated in a porcelain dish at 200° until no more acetic acid was evolved. The deep brown melt was cooled, extracted with ethanol, the extraction mixture was concentrated, cooled, whereby colourless product was precipitated which collected and crystallized from ethanol into colourless needles, m.p. 138-139°. Anal. Calcd. For $C_{18}H_{18}N_2OS$: C, 64.86; H, 4.05; N, 9.46. Found: C, 64.76; H, 4.15; N, 9.51.

2-Aryl-5-benzyl-oxazolo[4,5-b] phenothiazines(IX):

(i) Reaction of (I) with benzyl chloride and preparation of 2-phenyl-5-benzyl-oxazolo [4,5-b] phenothiazine (II), (Ar=C₆H₅):

Aminophenothiazone (1 mol) was covered with benzyl chloride (1 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on the direct flame for about 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the deposited solid was collected, washed with few drops of alcohol and crystallized from benzene, m.p. 310° not depressed on admixture with an authentic sample obtained by reaction of (I) with benzaldehyde as previously mentioned and the product was identified as 2-phenyl [4,5-b] oxazolophenothiazine (c.f. Table 1).

By refluxing I (1 mol) and benzyl chloride (2 mol) under the above conditions 2-phenyl-5-benzyl-oxazolo [4,5-b] phenothiazine was obtained, m.p. 235° (c.f. Table 2).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-H-OXAZOLO [4, 5-b] PHENOTHIAZINES (III).

(III), 2-Ar	M. P. °C	Solvent of crystall- ization	Calculated (%)			Molecular Formula	Found (%)		
			C	H	N		C	H	N
Phenyl	310	B	72.15	3.79	8.86	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	72.02	3.89	8.65
Cinnamyl	315-317	E	73.68	4.09	8.18	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	73.59	4.15	7.89
Anisyl	270	B	69.36	4.04	8.08	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.27	4.14	8.10
<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	240	B	65.14	3.14	8.00	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ SCI	65.40	3.32	8.19
Salicyl	312	P	68.67	3.61	8.43	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	68.80	3.72	8.13
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	335	Bu	63.33	3.06	11.66	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	63.41	3.21	11.51
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	230	Bu	63.33	3.06	11.66	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	63.25	3.30	11.45
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	298	Bu	63.33	3.06	11.66	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	63.48	3.51	11.30
<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	291	P	68.67	3.93	12.68	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	68.61	4.01	12.71
<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	297	P	68.67	3.93	12.68	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	68.52	3.75	12.65
<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	304	P	68.67	3.93	12.68	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	68.48	3.62	12.49

B benzene; E, ethanol, Bu, n-butanol, P, petroleum ether (80-100°).

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-BENZYL-OXAZOLO [4, 5-b] PHENOTHIAZINES (IX).

(IX), 2-Ar	M. P. °C	Solvent of crystall- ization	Calculated (%)			Molecular formula	Found (%)		
			C	H	N		C	H	N
Phenyl	235	E	76.84	4.43	6.89	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO	76.72	4.52	7.07
2-phenyl (<i>o</i> -ben- zyloxyphenyl)	240	E	77.34	4.71	5.47	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO ₂	77.52	4.90	5.23
<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	257	B	69.17	3.76	9.31	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.37	3.51	8.95
<i>m</i> -nitrophenyl	265	B	69.17	3.76	9.31	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.48	3.91	9.42
<i>o</i> -nitrophenyl	262	B	69.17	3.76	9.31	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.05	3.65	9.51
Anisyl	260	B	74.31	4.58	6.42	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	74.41	4.25	6.65

E = ethanol, B = benzene.

(ii) *Reaction of 2-aryloxazolophenothiazine with benzyl chloride and preparation of (IX)*: Oxazolophenothiazines III (1 mol) were covered with benzyl chloride (more than 1 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on the direct flame for about 2 hours. The excess benzyl chloride was removed, the reaction mixture was collected and the deposited solid was collected, washed with alcohol and crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are shown in Table 2.

Reduction of 2-nitro-aryloxazolophenothiazines: A finely powdered sample of the nitro-oxazolophenothiazines (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3 hr. with stannous chloride (0.02 mol) in the presence of alcoholic hydrogen chloride solution (50 ml). The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated aminohydrochloride was filtered and dried. The product was suspended in water, then treated with an equivalent amount of sodium carbonate solution. The free amine was collected and crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are shown in Table 1.

Preparation of oxazolophenothiazine dyes:^a

(i) *Diazotization of 2-(*p*-aminophenyl) oxazolo [4,5-*b*] phenothiazine*: Aminophenylloxazolophenothiazine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml), was cooled at 0°, and then nitrosylsulphuric

acid (5 ml, 0.0113 mol NaNO₂ in 5 ml conc. H₂SO₄) was added very slowly at such a rate that the temperature did not exceed 0°. When all the acid has been added, the mixture was allowed to stand in an ice bath for 30 min. with occasional stirring. The diazonium salt solution was poured onto ice (50 g.) and left to cool.

(ii) Disperse Dyes:

*Coupling of diazotized *p*-aminophenylloxazolophenothiazine with naphthols*: The calculated amount of freshly prepared diazonium salt of aminophenylloxazolophenothiazine was coupled with α - and β -naphthol (0.29 g. dissolved in 20 ml of 1 *N* NaOH solution). The reaction mixture was neutralized by the addition of sodium carbonate, whereas, with α -naphthol a reddish-brown dye was deposited, crystallized from ethanol into brown needles m.p. 280°. Anal. Calcd. For C₂₁H₁₇N₄O₂S: C, 73.08; H, 3.33; N, 11.00; Found: C, 73.21; H, 3.24; N, 11.12%, λ_{max} 495 ϵ_{max} 40125 with β -naphthol a pink dye was deposited and crystallized from methanol as red needles m.p. 249°. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₇N₄O₂S: C, 73.08; H, 3.33; N, 11.00. Found: C, 73.21; H, 3.42; N, 10.92, λ_{max} 480, ϵ_{max} 38210. Other dispersed dyes were obtained by coupling the above diazonium salt according to the normal procedures with naphthylamines and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone.

The prepared dyes were applied as disperse dyes on Nylon in acidic solution and showed good substantivity and satisfactory fastness properties.

(iii) *Direct Dyes* :

Coupling with J-acid and o-acid: This was proceeded normally in an alkaline medium to give a water-soluble reddish-violet dyes ; they were precipitated from the coupling mixture by the addition of sodium carbonate, showed satisfactory substantivity for dyeing cellulosic fibres in neutral solution, wool and nylon in acidic solution, with violet colour and sufficient fastness properties.

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